

GENDER DIFFERENCES IN COMMUNICATION IN THE WORKPLACE

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ABSTRACT

The analysis of the characteristics of gender differences occurring in the process of communication was highlighted in the article. Since gender linguistics is a new field of modern linguistics, it is described what language units women and men use in the process of communication.

Introduction:

Communication is one of the necessary conditions for the existence of human society. Communication is the most important communication tool used to express feelings, thoughts, ideas, and wishes between people. The process of communication is being studied in world science as an integral part of linguistics, psychology, history, logic, pedagogy and some other sciences.

Along with observations of traditional methods of analysis in linguistics, interest in new methods of analysis connecting it with sociology, psychology and other sciences is growing. New modern directions are emerging in linguistics related to these methods of analysis. One of such directions is linguo-genderology. The research source of this science is the study of the gender characteristics of the language, which includes two issues: the differences and characteristics of women's and men's speech; in the language system, attention is paid to language units that express concepts related to the signs of masculinity and femininity. In the study of gender issues in linguistics, all forms of speech activity: written and spoken texts can serve as research objects.

There are many works devoted to these issues in world linguistics. The reason why discourse is given special importance in the study of the language and gender problem is that many phenomena conditioned by the signs of femininity and masculinity, including feminine or masculine characteristics of speech, occur in speech. In this respect, revealing the gender characteristics of the discourse provides very interesting information. The term "discourse" is taken from the French language (*discours*) and means the form of oral speech of the text, dialogue, a set of comments connected to each other in terms of meaning, the meaning of a speech work. In the studies carried out in the Uzbek language, the term discourse means more oral text. In any interpretation, the discourse is inextricably linked with the concept of the

text. It should be noted that in linguistics, the issue of the relationship between the concepts of discourse and text has been the cause of scientific debate. At this point, the following opinions of linguist Sh. Safarov are reasonable: "It is appropriate to study these two phenomena being compared in the relationship of "hyperonym" - "hyponym".

Discourse is a certain type and series of human conscious activity, and the text is a manifestation of it. The interpretation of the category of discourse in such a broad sense, generalizing content, is already recognized rule for communication system, other fields of science interested in human conscious activity, such as philosophy, sociology, psychology, cybernetics. It is not difficult to determine the characteristics of women and men in the process of communication. At this point, it is appropriate to dwell on some gender features of the discourse. It was recommended to express our observations on the basis of a table. When it comes to the gender features of the discourse, the comparison of lexemes used in women's and men's speech is of particular importance.

Literature analysis and methods:

In the process of covering this article, descriptive and comparative methods of linguistics were used. The collection of scientific articles entitled "*Introduction to the theory and practice of gender relations*", the book "*Uzbek folk proverbs*" published in 2005 under the authorship of T. Mirzayev, A. Musoqulov, B. Sarimsakovlar serves as the main source.

Discussion:

There are several types of communication process: verbal and non-verbal communication. Verbal communication is the process of communicating through language. Non-verbal communication, which is obvious from the name, does not involve words. Facial expressions, pantomime, gestures, visual communication make up the non-verbal part of communication.

The speech of men and women also has its place in the complex social process called communication. As a confirmation of our opinion, it is enough to give an example of gender linguistics, a field that has been studied with great interest in linguistics in recent years. Gender linguistics is a widely researched field mainly in Western linguistics. In recent years, we are witnessing the rapid growth of the study of this field by linguists and sociologists of our country. Before, scientists did not pay much attention to the field of gender linguistics. But over time, this field attracted the attention of scientists and began to be studied in different paradigms.

Gender linguistics was first studied in the last years of the 20th century in Western linguistics and later in the East. The concept of "gender" was transferred to English from the Latin word *genus*, which means "gender".

The first attempt to differentiate the concepts of sex and gender was made in 1968 by Professor Robert Stoller of the University of California. In gender linguistics, it is deeply studied how women and men differ from each other in terms of communication. In general, there is a big difference in the speech of representatives of the two sexes.

There are words in our language that are used only by a representative of a certain gender. According to the researchers, women's speech is lexically, grammatically and phonetically different from men's speech. Linguists have concluded that 30% of women's speech consists of phrases. As a result of observations, the contrast between the speech of

women and men is clearly visible. To analyze this, first of all, let's talk about how women behave in different speech situations.

First, let's analyze the differences in the greeting process. If women see someone they know on the street or at work, they ask how they are doing. At this time, they talk about the topics they have talked about before without getting bored, and it is also often observed that they exaggerate what their friends have said to another person. Men often use one or two words in the process of greeting and like the conversation to be short and to the point. They often say "*Hello. Are you doing well?*" they end their conversation. Men think carefully before speaking on any subject and then express their opinion. This is another way that they are very different from women. Exaggeration and sarcasm can often be found in women's speech. But accuracy, fluency, correctness, brevity are often reflected in men's speech.

According to Western linguists, women get out of any situation faster and easier than men. This is due to the fact that women use more lies in their speech than men.

When it comes to feelings, it can be said that women are very expressive by nature and can easily express their feelings in front of other people. This is another proof that they are psychologically different from men. When women are chatting, time seems to fly by and they can talk for hours without stopping even on simple topics. Most women have a constant need to communicate. Most women like to talk to someone even during the short breaks at work.

The use of vocabulary is also chosen depending on which social group a woman or a man stands in front of. When we observe women in formal communication processes, we have often witnessed that they try to behave more seriously in such circles and speak less, not to use the words they use in the circle of their friends. Women express their opinions very carefully during such conversations. If they do not like the thoughts of the interlocutor, they often use abstract words in order not to offend or to avoid conflicts. For example, if they are not satisfied with the offer made by another person during the conclusion of the contract, they will say: "*How about we think about this matter one more time?*", "*How about we come back to this issue after a while?*", such expressions are widely used.

Men listen to the interlocutor's thoughts during the conversation and try not to interrupt their words too often. They do not like to brag during the conversation and avoid showing off their personal belongings. They believe that gossiping is unmanly and they practice it.

Proverbs reflecting gender characteristics can be found not only in the Uzbek language, but also in many other foreign languages. In particular, there are many female and male proverbs in the German language.

According to linguists, language renewal processes are accepted by men faster than women, and new scientific and professional lexemes are used more and more actively in men's speech. According to another linguist, women make good use of neologisms in everyday communication, while trying to avoid them in formal communication. Also, according to the use of evaluative adjectives, the speech of men and women differs. The active use of such units is recognized as one of the characteristic features of women's speech. Since a woman is created delicate by nature, she often uses attractive and colorful lexemes, words expressing personal attitude, especially lexemes with a positive connotation, during the conversation. Usually, the subject of the conversation is shown with a slight exaggeration. In the process of

conversation, emotionality is stronger in women: psycho-physiological states such as surprise, joy, frustration, and fear are more vividly reflected. The uniqueness of women's and men's speech is clearly visible when comparing the sentences used in their speech.

For example, when women express their agreement or disagreement with the interlocutor's opinion and their personal relationships, they construct sentences carefully so as not to offend the interlocutor, that is, to express their objections and displeasures they use more neutral constructions and molds.

As for general conclusions:

Gender is a multifaceted concept. Therefore, gender-related problems are the object of investigation in many fields. In particular, gender is being researched in various aspects in disciplines such as sociology, psychology, cognitology, and linguistics. Gender as a social device has a special place in the science of linguistics. Therefore, the most studied field of gender is linguistics.

Linguistic genderology, like any new direction, is a new direction in which the categories of the apparatus of concepts are not clearly formed. This new direction is in the process of forming its own research methods and methods. At the same time, scientists in the scientific field of linguistics use the methods of linguistic research and the methods of sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics and other humanitarian sciences (*linguistics, history, literary studies, etc.*).

In the study of gender issues in linguistics, all forms of speech activity: written and spoken texts can serve as research objects. There are many works devoted to these issues in world linguistics. The reason why discourse is given special importance in the study of the language and gender problem is that many phenomena conditioned by the signs of femininity and masculinity, including feminine or masculine characteristics of speech, occur in speech. In this respect, revealing the gender characteristics of the discourse provides very interesting information.

In the Uzbek language, like all languages in the world, thoughts are expressed not only linguistically, but also with the help of non-linguistic (*extralinguistic or paralinguistic*) means - gestures and implicit (*inseparable*) sounds. Gender differences can also be observed in non-verbal means that supplement speech. Therefore, it is necessary to research non-verbal means from the extralinguistic basis from the perspective of gender linguistics. Because men and women have their own facial expressions and gestures.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that gender is a multifaceted concept. This branch of linguistics is inextricably linked with all fields. During the interview, representatives of both sexes can be affected by various factors. Women, as mentioned above, enter the communication process easier and faster than men. Men, on the other hand, have a little difficulty in communicating, and if they are asked an off-topic question during a conversation, they do not answer these questions as much as possible. Differences between men and women are especially reflected in folk proverbs.

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